

Effect of solvent on the rate of oxidation of substituted anilines with nicotinium dichromate in aqueous-acetic acid media

D. S. Bhuvaneshwari and K. P. Elango*

Department of Chemistry, Gandhigram Rural Institute (Deemed University), Gandhigram-624 302, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : drkpelango@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 19 October 2005, revised 20 June 2006, accepted 7 July 2006

Abstract : Mechanistic studies on the oxidation of 15 *para*- and *meta*-substituted anilines by nicotinium dichromate in water-acetic acid medium of varying mole fractions have been performed. The reaction can be characterized by the experimental rate equation,

$$\frac{-d[\text{oxidizing agent}]}{dt} = \frac{Kk [\text{substrate}] [\text{HCrO}_4^-]}{(1 + K [\text{substrate}])}$$

The addition of *p*-toluenesulfonic acid enhances the reaction. The oxidation substituted anilines at 299–322 K complies with the isokinetic relationship but not to any of the linear free energy relationships, the isokinetic temperature lies within the experimental range. Correlation of rate data with Kamlet-Taft solvatochromic parameters (α , β , π^*) suggests that the specific solute-solvent interactions play a major role in governing the reactivity.

Keywords : Solvent effect, nicotinium dichromate, oxidation, substituted anilines.

The kinetic studies of oxidation of organic compounds in non-aqueous and aquo-organic solvent media has revealed the important role of non-specific and specific solvent effects on the reactivity. It has been shown that the reactivity is influenced by the preferential solvation of the reactants and/or the transition state through non-specific and specific solvent-solvent-solute interactions. Furthermore, it has been established that the technique of correlation analysis may well be used to separate, quantify and rationalize such solvent-solvent-solute interactions on reactivity¹.

Further, one of the important tools in deciding the mechanism of reactions is the study of substituent effects and thermodynamic parameters. The Hammett equation and its modified forms², all known as Linear Free Energy Relationships (LFER) have been found useful for correlating reaction rates and equilibrium constants for side chain reactions for *meta*- and *para*-substituted derivatives. The isokinetic relationship is also an important tool for deciding the nature of a mechanism. Keeping this in view, a systematic study of various LFERs and the isokinetic relationship has been made to establish the role of solvent and substituents on reactivity and to decide the

nature of the mechanism being followed in the nicotinium dichromate³ (NDC, a mild and selective oxidant) oxidation of some *meta*- and *para*-substituted anilines.

Results and discussion

The kinetic studies were carried out under pseudo-first-order conditions with the $[\text{substrate}] \gg [\text{NDC}]$. The first-order dependence of the reaction on NDC is obvious from the linearity of the plots of $\log [\text{NDC}]$ versus time. Further, the pseudo-first-order rate constants, k_{obs} , do not depend on the initial concentration of NDC (Table 1). At fixed $[\text{NDC}]$, the rate of oxidation increases with increasing $[\text{substrate}]$. The plot of k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[\text{substrate}]^{-1}$ is linear with definite intercept on the rate ordinate, which indicates the operation of Michaelis-Menten mechanism for the oxidation process.

where K is the equilibrium constant for the formation of Michaelis-Menten complex, and k the rate constant for

Table 1. Pseudo-first-order rate constants ($10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$, s^{-1}) for the oxidation of aniline by NDC in aqueous acetic acid medium at 299 K

10^2 [Aniline] (M)	10^3 [NDC] (M)	10^3 [H ⁺] (M)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s^{-1})
2.0	1.00	1.0	2.27
2.0	1.25	1.0	2.32
2.0	1.50	1.0	2.19
2.0	1.75	1.0	2.30
2.0	1.0	1.0	0.61
2.0	1.0	2.0	1.14
2.0	1.0	3.0	2.27
2.0	1.0	4.0	5.51
2.0	1.0	2.0	2.10 ^a

^aContained 0.001 M, Mn^{II}.

the decomposition of Michaelis-Menten complex. Usually first step is a fast pre-equilibrium and the electron-transfer step is rate determining. The pseudo-first-order rate constant reads, under [substrate] > [NDC] :

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k K [\text{substrate}]}{1 + K [\text{substrate}]}$$

According to the above equation k and K could be separately determined just by employing different excess of

the substrate and plotting k_{obs}^{-1} versus [substrate]⁻¹ and the estimated values are given in Table 2. The oxidation of aniline by NDC was found to be catalyzed by presence of *p*-toluenesulfonic acid (TsOH) and the k_{obs} values increase with increase in the initial concentration of TsOH (Table 1). Catalysis by *p*-toluenesulfonic acid suggests hydrolysis of the NDC species rather than the protonation of the aniline molecule, which would have resulted in rate retardation⁴. The reaction did not promote polymerization of acrylonitrile indicating absence of free radicals. However, addition of Mn^{II}, in the form of MnSO₄, retard the rate of the oxidation process indicating two electron oxidation⁵.

The activation parameters were calculated from k at 299, 307, 315 and 322 K using the Eyring relationship by the method of least squares and are collected in Table 3. In an isoentropic oxidation the isokinetic temperature lies at infinite and only enthalpy of activation determines the rate. The isokinetic temperature is zero for an isoenthalpic series and the rate depends on the entropy of activation⁶. In the present study, the activation enthalpy of the decomposition of Michaelis-Menten complex is linearly related to activation entropy (Fig. 1, $r = 0.990$, $sd = 2.98$, $\Psi = 0.15$, isokinetic temperature = 323 ± 13 K). The validity of the isokinetic relationship suggests that the decomposition of Michaelis-Menten complexes

Table 2. Rate constant and equilibrium constant for the oxidation of *meta*- and *para*-substituted anilines by NDC

Mole fraction of AcOH	Substituents in aniline moiety														
	<i>para</i> -position									<i>meta</i> -position					
	H	Me	OMe	COMe	NHCOMe	NO ₂	Cl	Br	F	Me	COOH	NO ₂	Et	OMe	COMe
	$10^5 k, \text{s}^{-1}$														
0.3	250	58	13	12	808	8	11	9	7	40	2	4	19	65	16
0.4	330	93	22	21	903	11	14	10	11	46	4	6	35	103	40
0.5	332	122	26	43	744	12	20	14	20	144	6	7	76	240	48
0.6	558	183	42	66	893	19	32	17	30	197	7	9	158	464	71
0.7	832	213	57	83	1480	40	40	24	36	311	10	16	206	804	199
0.8	896	338	200	147	5441	66	40	64	53	336	25	20	292	1096	599
0.9	944	460	261	311	4365	79	77	97	150	381	102	44	375	1238	1163
	$K, \text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$														
0.3	1	50	162	247	20	84	63	82	104	31	78	65	53	109	16
0.4	15	39	83	106	19	87	73	95	122	30	21	41	28	78	9
0.5	1	52	89	49	29	143	97	91	69	10	22	55	15	29	10
0.6	2	82	48	78	28	92	198	130	98	11	700	58	10	26	33
0.7	17	154	60	146	18	54	177	177	205	10	127	45	13	17	19
0.8	1	88	29	167	5	58	325	103	123	10	38	66	37	42	8
0.9	3	108	37	79	10	251	119	75	126	28	15	62	24	58	9

Table 3. Effect of temperature on the rate of oxidation of anilines by NDC in 0.7 mole fraction of acetic acid in water and activation parameters for the oxidation

Substituents	Rate constants $10^5 k$ (s^{-1})				E_a	ΔH^\ddagger	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	ΔG^\ddagger
	299 K	307 K	315 K	322 K				
in aniline								
H	832	1117	3074	4256	49.1	47.1	-125	84.6
<i>p</i> -Me	213	320	359	438	16.8	16.9	-238	88.1
<i>p</i> -OMe	56	160	214	442	53.6	51.5	-130	90.6
<i>p</i> -COMe	83	311	327	705	53.6	51.7	-126	89.4
<i>p</i> -NHCOMe	1480	1514	2088	2332	14.0	12.0	-239	83.6
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	40	66	94	108	27.5	25.4	-222	92.1
<i>p</i> -Cl	40	67	110	171	40.2	38.1	-180	92.0
<i>p</i> -Br	24	123	183	245	60.9	59.3	-109	92.0
<i>p</i> -F	36	88	155	180	44.5	42.5	-164	91.8
<i>m</i> -Me	311	322	329	394	6.1	4.1	-279	87.6
<i>m</i> -COOH	9	17	30	94	61.0	58.9	-122	95.5
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	16	61	99	100	49.1	53.6	-132	93.3
<i>m</i> -Et	175	202	206	240	8.1	6.0	-277	88.9
<i>m</i> -OMe	349	505	601	804	22.2	20.3	-222	86.9
<i>m</i> -COMe	199	211	269	326	14.4	12.3	-255	88.6

[Substrate] = 5×10^{-2} M; [NDC] = 1×10^{-3} M; [TsOH] = 2×10^{-2} M.

E_a kJ mol⁻¹ K⁻¹, ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol⁻¹, ΔS^\ddagger J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹, ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol⁻¹.

Fig. 1. Isokinetic relationship for the oxidation of anilines by NDC in 0.7 mole fraction of acetic acid in water.

Fig. 2. Isokinetic plot for the oxidation of aniline by NDC in varying mole fraction of acetic acid in water.

follow a common mechanism.

Since the reactions are of ion-dipolar type, it is expected that the entropy of the activated complex for all these anilines should be nearly of the same order of magnitude. However, because of difference in the polarity of

different anilines, the extent of solvation should be different and hence the experimental value of ΔS^\ddagger may be different for different anilines⁷.

The activation energies and the entropies and enthalpies of activation for the decomposition of the Michaelis-

Table 4. Effect of temperature on the oxidation of unsubstituted aniline by NDC in different mole fractions of acetic acid in water and the activation parameters

<i>m.f.</i> of AcOH	Rate constants $10^5 k$ (s^{-1})				E_a	ΔH^\ddagger	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	ΔG^\ddagger
	299 K	307 K	315 K	322 K				
0	45	64	79	93	19.5	17.4	-249	92.0
0.1	59	81	82	133	20.2	18.1	-245	91.4
0.2	116	192	355	821	53.7	51.7	-126	89.4
0.3	255	354	808	1784	27.0	24.8	-210	87.7
0.4	330	491	601	749	20.1	20.1	-223	87.0
0.5	533	679	728	795	10.5	8.5	-259	86.0
0.6	441	776	1603	2082	44.7	42.6	-144	85.9
0.7	832	1117	3074	4256	49.1	47.1	-125	84.6
0.8	1514	2218	4307	6063	40.1	38.1	-150	83.1
0.9	3848	4257	7786	15831	40.3	38.2	-143	81.1
1.0	3011	3585	6363	8707	31.2	29.2	-175	81.6

[Substrate] = $5 \times 10^{-2} M$; [NDC] = $1 \times 10^{-3} M$; [TsOH] = $2 \times 10^{-2} M$.

E_a kJ mol $^{-1}$ K $^{-1}$, ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol $^{-1}$, ΔS^\ddagger J K $^{-1}$ mol $^{-1}$, ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol $^{-1}$.

Menten complex were also calculated for the unsubstituted aniline in different mole fractions of acetic acid in water (Table 4). The existence of a linear relationship (Fig. 2, $r = 0.975$, $sd = 3.23$, $\Psi = 0.24$, isokinetic temperature = 261 ± 19 K) between ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger indicates that a single mechanism is operating in all the solvent systems studied. A solvent change from water to AcOH in water causes rate acceleration for the reaction which corresponds to a decrease in ΔG^\ddagger by ~ 10 kJ mol $^{-1}$. This decrease in ΔG^\ddagger indicates that the activated complex is solvated extensively by the solvent mixture⁸. Negative entropy of activation indicates a greater degree of ordering in the transition state than in the initial state, due to an increase in solvation during the activation process. The results in Table 4 show that the largest k values are obtained in the less polar solvent mixtures correspond to the decrease in activation entropy. This observation can be rationalized because polar mixtures will have some structure corresponding to the orientation of the dipolar solvent molecules due to intermolecular solvent-solvent interactions. In less polar mixtures, however, which have only a small or no dipole moment; the solvent molecules will be relatively unoriented and consequently have higher entropy. Thus, less-polar mixtures will have a greater entropy loss as a result of increased solvation during activation process. Hence, it is presumed that, in the present study, solvent-solvent interactions play a significant role, in addition to solute-solvent interactions, in governing the rate of the reaction⁸.

Structure-reactivity correlation :

The decomposition of the Michaelis-Menten complexes of the listed 15 *para*- and *meta*-substituted anilines was analyzed in terms of the Hammett equation. The usual Hammett equation; $\log k$ (*para*- and *meta*- collectively and separately) versus σ plot is a scatter gram. The oxidation rates of *para*- and *meta*-substituted anilines are correlated separately with Hammett σ^- and Brown-Okamoto σ^+ but also without success. The failure of the single parameter equations to correlate the rate data leads to the possibility of operation of dual substituent parameter (DSP) equations. All the DSP equations including the Swain *et al.* equation fail to account for the variation of the rate with the substituent. The σ_I and σ_R values used are those reported by Dayal *et al.*⁹. The F and R values are those of Swain *et al.*¹⁰. The possible reason for the lack of any Linear Free Energy Relationship is that the isokinetic temperature falls within the experimental temperature. It is pertinent to note that the compensation law may lead to artifact¹¹.

Solvent-reactivity correlation :

The reaction has been studied in varying mole fractions of acetic acid in water with a range of *ca.* 43 units of relative permittivity. The influence of relative permittivity on the rate can be described by the Laidler and Eyring¹² equation,

$$d \ln k/d(1/\epsilon_r) = e^2 Z^2 (1/r - 1/r^*)/2kT$$

where k is the rate constant, Z the net charge, r the effective

tive radius and r^* is the radius of the activated species. The correlation of the rate constants for the decomposition of the Michaelis-Menten complexes with inverse of relative permittivity through the above equation is just satisfactory with an average explained variance, $100 r^2$, of 90%. The slope of the correlation is positive which suggests that the transition state is less polar than the reactants.

The solvent effect was also analyzed using the Grunwald-Winstein¹³ equation,

$$\log k = \log k_0 + mY$$

where Y is an empirical solvent parameter (solvent ionizing power) characteristic of the given solvent and m is a substrate parameter measuring the substrate sensitivity to changes in the ionizing power of the medium. The correlation of the rate constants for the decomposition of the Michaelis-Menten complexes with the solvent ionizing power, Y , is good (Fig. 3). The slope of the correlation is

Fig. 3. Grunwald-Winstein plot.

positive which also suggests the formation of a less polar transition state during the course of the reaction. Further, such a transition state will be stabilized by a less polar medium and hence an increase in rate of oxidation with an increase in mole fraction of acetic acid in the mixture.

From idealized theories, the solvent parameters ϵ_r and Y are often predicted to serve as a quantitative measure of solvent polarity. However, this approach is often inadequate since these theories regard solvents as a non-struc-

tured continuum, not composed of individual solvent molecules with their own solvent-solvent interactions and they do not take into account specific solute-solvent interactions, such as hydrogen bonding and electron pair donor-electron pair acceptor interactions, which often play a dominating role in solute-solvent interactions. No single macroscopic physical parameter could possibly account for the multitude of solute-solvent interactions on the molecular microscopic level. Thus, bulk solvent properties like ϵ_r and Y will poorly describe the microenvironment around the reacting species, which governs the stability of the transition state and hence the rate of the reaction. Hence, there have been a variety of attempts to quantify different aspects of solvent polarity and then use the resultant parameters to interpret solvent effects on reactivity through multiple regressions.

In order to obtain a deeper insight into the various solvent-solvent-solute interactions, which influence reactivity, we have tried to adopt the solvatochromic comparison method developed by Kamlet and Taft¹⁴. This method may be used to unravel, quantify, correlate and rationalize multiple interacting solvent effects on reactivity. The kinetic data were correlated with the solvatochromic parameters α , β and π^* characteristic of the different solvents in the form of the following LSER,

$$\log k = A_0 + s \pi^* + a \alpha + b \beta$$

where π^* is an index of solvent dipolarity/polarizability, which measures the ability of the solvent to stabilize a charge or a dipole by virtue of its dielectric effect, α is the solvent HBD (hydrogen bond donor) acidity, β is the solvent HBA (hydrogen bond acceptor) basicity of the solvent in a solute to solvent hydrogen bond and A_0 is the regression value of the solute property in the reference solvent cyclohexane. The regression coefficients s , a and b measure the relative susceptibilities of the solvent dependent solute property $\log k$ to the indicated solvent parameter. The solvatochromic parameters employed in the present study were from the literature¹⁵. The rates of the decomposition of the Michaelis-Menten complexes studied show an excellent correlation with solvent via the above LSER with an explained variance of *ca.* 97% and a representative result is given below.

For *p*-Cl substituted aniline :

$$\log k = A_0 - 3.85 \pi^* + 4.93 \alpha + 14.75 \beta$$

$$(R^2 = 0.971, sd = 0.05, \psi = 0.22, P_\alpha = 21\%,$$

$$P_\beta = 63\%, P_{\pi^*} = 16\%)$$

Such an excellent correlation indicates the existence of

both specific and non-specific solute-solvent-solvent interactions in the present study. From the values of the regression coefficients the contribution of each parameter, on a percentage basis, to reactivity was calculated as reported earlier¹⁶. The observation of this systematic multiple regression analysis leads us to the following conclusions. (i) The rate of the reaction is strongly influenced by specific solute-solvent interactions as indicated by the percentage contributions of α and β parameters. (ii) The results indicate that the contribution of HBA basicity (represented by β term) to the total solvent effect was found to be predominant. The sign of the coefficients of this term is positive indicating the better solvation of the transition state compared to the reactants. Though water and acetic acid are amphiprotic solvents, AcOH is protogenic i.e. is a weaker base than water⁸. It was well established that there must be a parallelism among three neat solvent properties i.e. cation-solvating tendency, HBA basicity and nucleophilicity⁸. Hence increase in the mole fraction of acetic acid in the mixture decreases the basicity of the medium. Thus, increase in rate with increase in the mole fraction of acetic acid in the mixture suggests that the transition state is less cationic in nature when compared to the reactants and such a transition state will be stabilized by a medium with a lesser basicity. (iii) The rate of the reaction is also influenced, to an appreciable extent, by π^* which is a measure of the solvent to stabilize a charge or a dipole by virtue of its dielectric effect. The negative sign of the coefficients of this term suggests that with decrease in polarizability/dipolarity of the medium the rate of the oxidation process will increase and hence an increase in rate of the reaction with increase in mole fraction of acetic acid in the medium is observed in the present investigation. This observation together with the parallelism between rate increase and decrease in the solvent basicity suggests that specific solvation and stabilization of the transition state by the solvent mixture play a dominant role in the reaction. Very likely, formation of a less polar (less cationic in nature) complex between the reactants in a rapid pre-equilibrium step precedes the rate-controlling step⁸.

Alternatively, water-acetic acid mixture is classified, by Blandamer and Burgess¹⁷ on the basis of thermodynamic properties particularly their molar excess functions X^E , as a typically non-aqueous positive (TNAP) mixture for which G^E is positive. Further, an extra thermodynamic analysis indicates that, at least qualitatively, if G^E is positive the solute should be more soluble in the mixture than predicted from the solubilities in the two pure solvents. Hence, in the present study, it is presumed that the increase in rate, with increase in the mole fraction of

acetic acid in the mixture, may be due to the fact that the transition state is more hydrophobic than the initial state and such a transition state will be stabilized in a TNAP solvent mixture consequently enhance the rate of the reaction.

Mechanism : In aqueous and partly aqueous media dichromate is hydrolyzed and in acidic solution the speciation of chromium(VI) are CrO_4^{2-} , HCrO_4^- and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ besides other protonated species such as $\text{H}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$, HCr_2O_7^- and H_2CrO_4 . A thorough study on the abundance of various Cr^{VI} species are available in literature and which reveal that the most abundant chromium(VI) species in the reaction solution is acid chromate ion¹⁸.

The oxidations are first-order in NDC and increases with acid concentration. The Michaelis-Menten dependence of the oxidation rates on [substrate] confirms formation of complexes in a rapid pre-equilibrium. Experiments reveal involvement of Cr^{IV} intermediate in the oxidation of anilines by Cr^{VI} containing reagent; Mn^{II} ion suppresses the oxidation rates. Manganese(II) ion reduces Cr^{IV} formed to Cr^{III} . In the absence of Mn^{II} ion, Cr^{IV} formed reduces Cr^{VI} to Cr^{V} . The oxidation of aniline by Cr^{V} is fast¹⁸.

Scheme 1

The suggested mechanism leads to the rate law

$$\frac{-d[\text{oxidizing agent}]}{dt} = \frac{Kk [\text{substrate}] [\text{HCrO}_4^-]}{(1 + K [\text{substrate}])}$$

The above rate law is in agreement with all the experimental findings, viz. the first-order in oxidant and the Michaelis-Menten dependence of the rate on [substrate]. The products separated suggest the formation of phenylhydroxylamine, indicating *N* attack otherwise azobenzene would not have been possible. Formation of azobenzene from phenylhydroxylamine and the subsequent oxidation products are as follows :

Having decided the site of attack, the next point to require consideration is the manner of electron transfer.

Conflicting ideas have been prevailing as to the true mechanism operative in Cr^{VI} oxidations¹⁹. The two mechanisms proposed are (i) direct hydride ion loss in a concerted process and (ii) prior formation of an ester in a reversible step, preceding the loss of a hydride ion. In the present study kinetics and solvent variation study and the results of the correlation of rate data with solvent parameters favours our choice of the second mechanism i.e. reversible formation of an ester (very likely concerted transfer of oxygen from HCrO₄⁻ to N-atom and electron pair from N-atom to Cr^{VI} leading to the formation of a complex which is less cationic in nature) preceding the H⁻ loss,

Experimental

Materials : All the chemicals and solvents used were of high purity analytical grade. The solid anilines were used as such and the liquid anilines were used after vacuum distillation. Nicotinium dichromate (NDC) was prepared by reported method and standardized iodometrically³.

Kinetic measurements : The reaction was initiated by adding NDC to the substrate. The progress of the oxidation, with aniline in large excess, was followed by iodometric estimation of the unconsumed oxidizing agent. The pseudo-first-order rate constants, k_{obs} , were determined by least squares method, from the linear plots ($r > 0.96$) of log [NDC] versus time. Replicate runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The reaction was carried out in varying mole fractions (0.3–0.9) of acetic acid in water at 26, 34, 42 and 49 (± 0.1) °C and the activation parameters were computed.

Correlation analyses were carried out using Microcal origin (version 6) computer software. The goodness of the fit was discussed using correlation coefficient (r in the case of simple linear regression and R in the case of multiple linear regression), standard deviation, sd , and Exner's statistical parameter, Ψ . The percentage contribution (P_x) of a parameter to the total effect on reactivity was computed using the regression coefficient of each parameter as reported earlier¹⁶.

The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by carrying out several sets of experiments with varying amounts of [NDC] largely in excess over [aniline]. The estimation of unreacted NDC showed that three moles of aniline reacts with one mole of NDC.

Product analysis : The oxidation product was analyzed using preparative TLC on silica gel, which yielded azobenzene m.p. 66 °C (lit. 68 °C), UV (EtOH) λ_{max}

320 nm and was confirmed using IR spectra by comparing with the authentic sample.

References

- 1 D S Bhuvaneshwari and K P Elango, *Z Naturforsch* . 2005, **60b**, 1105, G Fatuma Jeyanthi and K P Elango, *Int J Chem Kinet* , 2003, **35**, 154, S Saravanakanna and K P Elango, *Int J Chem Kinet* , 2002, **34**, 585, J R C Ramya Vijayakumari and K P Elango, *J Indian Chem Soc* , 2002, **79**, 834, K P Elango, *J Serb Chem Soc* , 2001, **66**, 359, M Harati and M R Cholami, *Int J Chem Kinet* , 2005, **37**, 90, M Khurana, P K Sharma and K K Banerji, *Proc Indian Acad Sci* , 2000, **112**, 73
- 2 J Shorter, "Correlation Analysis of Organic Reactivity", Research Studies Press, Letchworth, 1982
- 3 C Lopez, A Gonzalez, F P Cossio and C Palomo, *Synth Commun* , 1985, **15**, 1197
- 4 G P Panigrahi and D D Mahapatro, *Int J Chem Kinet* , 1982, **14**, 977
- 5 G Karthikeyan, K P Elango and K Karunakaran, *J Indian Chem Soc* , 1997, **74**, 798
- 6 C Karunakaran and P N Palanisamy, *Gaz Chim Ita* , 1997, **127**, 559
- 7 S P Srivastava, V K Gupta, M C Jain, M N Ansari and R D Kaushik, *Thermochim Acta*, 1983, **68**, 27
- 8 C. Reichardt, "Solvents and Solvent Effects in Organic Chemistry", VCH, Weinheim, 1988
- 9 S K Dayal, S Ehrenson and R W Taft, *J Am Chem Soc* , 1972, **94**, 9113
- 10 C G Swain, S H Unger, N R Rosenquist and M S Swain, *J Am Chem Soc* , 1983, **105**, 492
- 11 W Linert, *Chem Soc Rev.*, 1994, **23**, 429
- 12 A S Amis and J I Hinton, "Solvent Effect of Chemical Phenomena", Academic Press, New York, 1973
- 13 A H Fainberg and S Winstein, *J Am Chem Soc* , 1956, **78**, 2770
- 14 M J. Kamlet, J M Abboud, M H Abraham and R W Taft, *J Org Chem* , 1983, **48**, 2877
- 15 Y Marcus, *J Chem Soc* , *Perkin Trans 2*, 1994, 1751
- 16 C Reichardt, *Angew Chem Int Ed (Eng)* , 1979, **18**, 98
17. M J Blandamer and J Burgess, *Chem Soc Rev* , 1975, **4**, 55
- 18 C Karunakaran and S Suresh, *J Phys Org Chem* , 2004, **17**, 88, C Karunakaran, S. Karuthapandian and S Suresh, *Int J Chem Kinet.*, 2003, **35**, 1, K B Wiberg, "Oxidation in Organic Chemistry", Part A, Academic Press, New York, 1965
- 19 K Mahanthi and K K Banerji, *J Indian Chem Soc* , 2002, **79**, 31